

Research

Identifying and Ranking Factors Affecting Organizational Loyalty and Tenure of Faculty Members in Mashhad University of Medical Sciences by the Hierarchical Method

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Abstract: Background and purpose: One of the important challenges of organizational universities is the gap between academic space and university needs. Faculty members, as the life-giving heart of the university and the main factor in achieving its goals, have always been one of the centers of attention of higher education administrators. The problem is the lack of compatibility between the abilities, activities, and outputs of faculty members with the needs of the university, which manifests itself as a problem of lack of motivation of faculty members.

Research method: The current research is applied in terms of purpose and descriptive survey in terms of type. The statistical population of the research was the faculty members of Mashhad University of Medical Sciences with at least a doctorate and ten years of experience. Stratified random sampling is the mechanism used and the number is 245 people. Based on previous research, background factors were identified and 41 propositions in the form of 3 factors and 3 predisposed outcomes were selected using the opinion of the expert group. Then, the questionnaire tool was designed and implemented for the pairwise comparison of indicators using the hierarchical analysis method.

Findings: According to the subjects, indicators of environmental factors and organizational factors were more important than other indicators, and indicators of organizational commitment and organizational belonging were of little importance.

Discussion and conclusion: access to scientific resources, information, and modern technology, as well as the decent and respectful behavior of the manager with the employees, are among the strong points of the reasons for the organizational loyalty and longevity of the faculty members of Mashhad University of Medical Sciences, which requires controlling the satisfaction of the appointment according to the services and The qualification is individual; Because it is associated with significant complexity due to the nature of medical activities. However, the lack of access to alternative jobs and the use of information dissemination are among its weaknesses, and it requires control of the supply of equipment and knowledge required for high-tech industries.

Keywords: faculty members, academic staff; durability, Organizational loyalty.

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Introduction

Today, universities are competing in many fields, including aspects of student and faculty management at the national and international levels. They need credibility, and reputation, produce high-level research work to keep students and faculty members satisfied, and respond to the growing needs of society. Accordingly, universities and higher education centers are surrounded by powerful forces, the demand for higher education is increasing day by day, and due to the increase in unemployment and economic crises, people are trying to find a university degree by acquiring expertise and university degrees. and prepare for a suitable job. Therefore, higher education should provide better services and education to people so that it can continue to play a role as a source of growth and development of the human resources of society. The most important factor that can help the higher education system achieve this goal is the human resources active in higher education and its faculty members. The presence of highly qualified professors and the continuous improvement of faculty members can play an effective role in this matter.

According to some experts, the essence of higher education is summed up in the faculty the faculty is the heart of every university, and the quality and effectiveness of a university depends on its faculty members (1). On the one hand, evidence and studies indicate that the quality of university science and higher education in Iran has become extremely important (2) and it indicates the prevalence of some kind of abnormality in the culture of knowledge production and dissemination among the new generation of faculty members (3). For this reason, the officials of the universities, including the organizational university under study, who have always been concerned about meeting the needs and reducing the gap between themselves and the needs of the society and the respective organization, to the faculty members for their great influence on the outputs of the university and the narrowing of the mentioned gap deserves special attention. Based on this, the challenge considered in this study was to properly fulfill the assigned roles such as student education, science production, and in general, solving the problems of society and the university (central organization).

Currently, the central organization expects more and better outputs (in accordance with the issues of the organization), dynamism and a higher scientific level from the university and faculty. On the other hand, the symptoms of the problem indicated its complexity. A witness to this claim is that sometimes some professors from other universities are used and establish parallel research centers with the university. University policies such as increasing the intensity of supervision and control and creating structures and regulations have not been able to have a great effect on improving the problem. Although the studies have been sporadic in introducing these factors of occurrence and strengthening of these behaviors. But the unification and design of the pattern of these studies, which seems to be a theoretical vacuum in the research literature, and on the other hand, its refinement according to the ecology of Mashhad University of Medical Sciences, can provide the basis for increasing the productivity of human resources in recruitment, training, development and strengthening. to oversee human resources in Mashhad University of Medical Sciences and in this way make the direction of future research clearer. Therefore, the review of the literature on the issue under discussion indicates a research gap in this field, especially in the field of organizational university faculty, which shows the importance of addressing this issue and is also considered one of the limitations of the research.

The feeling of loyalty to the organization makes employees work with more motivation, and as a result, their output will be far better, and the productivity of human resources will be higher. This motivation in employees will cause

loyalty to the organization, a sense of commitment, belonging, and job satisfaction. Employees who are loyal to the organization feel responsible for the goals of the organization, work in line with these goals, and implement the managers' decisions. A person who is loyal to the organization accepts changes in the organization faster and with greater satisfaction and adapts to them. gives, because he considers himself a part of the organization and understands the policies of the organization (4). Loyalty to the organization and the long-term persistence of people in the organization will lead to the unification and more relationships of employees in an organization, which will create intimacy and effective communication among employees and subsequently increase the motivation and desire to work in the organization. Communication between employees and members of a group in the organization, which is known as lateral relations, is a direct channel for coordinating and solving the problems of the organization and includes an important part of employee satisfaction.

For effective communication, there are perceived barriers that include; Differences in perception, differences in language, voice, emotions, inconsistency in verbal and non-verbal communication, and lack of trust (5); As can be seen, many of these obstacles, such as differences in perception and differences in language, lack of trust and emotions, and other issues, will be resolved to some extent by the continuous and long-term communication of employees with each other and will be less effective. Some of these obstacles, such as the lack of trust among employees, are caused by their lack of knowledge of each other, with the constant entry and exit of employees, these problems will remain continuous and multiply, and incomplete and ineffective communication will prevail in the organization. which will eventually weaken the organization.

Theoretical

Faculty members are the most valuable and vital assets of any university and identifying the challenges and obstacles in the activities of these people and investing in their growth and excellence as the most important strategy in the growth of the university and laying the groundwork for moving towards scientific authority. It is very important (6). In general, one of the major challenges that the country's higher education is currently facing is the quantitative and qualitative development and growth of university faculty members; More and more, they need a deeper understanding of scientific and technological developments, the growing social demand for higher education and a new image of their scientific, educational, research and cultural activities in the university (7).

Today, in the field of higher education, universities have dramatically entered the competitive market and are adopting the management styles and approaches of the private and industrial sectors. This issue is seen in the competition to attract faculty members with strong scientific and research skills and capabilities (8) and high performance (9). Human resource management professionals in higher education should behave like their private sector counterparts who believe that companies can create a competitive advantage through "talented human resources"; Because employees are unique (8).

Faculty members are the most valuable organizational resources in higher education, and due to the increasing complexity and growth of academic centers, the importance of hiring, maintaining, and developing talented faculty is important (10). Talent resources are known as strategic resources because of their ability to create a competitive advantage and influence the performance of universities (11). Nowadays, universities have increasingly realized that conscious and deliberate identification of talents is very important to maximize their performance (12). Therefore, universities must actively manage their talents and prevent wasting and losing talents; Meanwhile, human resource management

specialists are always facing problems to identify talents (13). It should be emphasized that despite the very hot topic of "talent" among human resource professionals, few previous research has analyzed talent (14, 15), which often focuses on talent management (8, 16); But the question of what exactly needs to be managed has been largely ignored. On the other hand, the failure to identify talents may lead to negative consequences regarding the loss of key talents and the direct costs associated with it, including recruitment and reduced performance indirect costs: loss of special and specialized skills (17), which in this context, the research results show that higher education institutions have failed in maintaining their talented faculty members.

The importance of identifying, attracting, and retaining talented faculty members is such that this issue is rapidly becoming a key and important category for human resource management in universities (18). The composition and quality of faculty members are important for the quality of educational and research programs of universities, as well as the reputation and competitive position of universities (19). In recent years, the topic of employee motivation and its role in the productivity of people (20) and the greater benefit of employees (21) has attracted the attention of many researchers and successful organizations try to have purposeful behavior in employees. self-create Therefore, one of the important issues that can be investigated at the level of organizations and work environments, and is of particular importance, is the issue of the existence of efficient and self-motivated human resources. Despite all these technological advances, human issues are still the biggest problem of organizations of our time (20). One of the most important resources of any organization is human resources; The constituents of this force are people with countless needs who will use their talents and skills in the service of the organization if their needs are met and they have sufficient motivation. The success and progress of the university also depend on its human resources, which play an essential role in the social, economic, cultural, and political development of societies. The results of studies conducted in developed and developing countries show that the efficiency and effectiveness of the educational system of each country is an indicator of comprehensive development (22).

Strong motivation and willingness to work are the main factors in creating effort and undertaking personal activities. Career motivation and satisfaction of faculty members play a key role in their performance. Failure to pay attention to their satisfaction will lead to relative suspension and passivity within the organization and ultimately cause the gradual downfall of the organization; If the university officials are not able to attract and maintain competent and motivated human resources, the university will face difficulties in fulfilling its important responsibilities and duties. Cultivating such forces is very costly and time-consuming, and since professors and teachers were important and respected throughout the history of all societies, considering their role as role models among people; Recognizing their motivation factors, and providing them makes teachers look more effective, be more successful in their work and enjoy it; Also, logical relationships with students strengthen study and creativity (21), increase the output of the organization, increase the level of sustainability, productivity and work performance (22) and cause the survival of the organization in the environment. Also, due to being aware of and mastering many of their environmental and social behaviors, professors need special motivations that are different from other strata and social classes (23); Therefore, universities should equip them for educational and research activities by meeting their material and spiritual needs and creating a suitable working environment; Because shirking the duties or reducing the productivity of working faculty members may become a real threat to the effectiveness of the university (24).

Research background

In the current research, a regular and coherent protocol was used for a background search, in which the keywords pattern, belonging, commitment, organizational loyalty, and durability were searched. Also, the final sources of each article and other research cited in them were checked to find the background. Among the conducted research, the closest studies to the current research are the case studies that have been conducted in recent years and some of them are mentioned below.

Gham Shadzehi and Nasti Zaei conducted research titled "Investigating the relationship between spirituality at work and job attachment with the mediating role of organizational loyalty (case study: elementary school teachers in Khash city)". The findings indicate the direct effect of spirituality at work on job attachment, the direct effect of spirituality at work on organizational loyalty, and the direct effect of organizational loyalty on job attachment. with the difference that spirituality at work had an indirect effect on job attachment with the mediating role of organizational loyalty (25). Ghanbari and Abdul Maleki conducted research titled "Ethical leadership's role in organizational loyalty with the mediation of belongingness" and concluded that ethical leadership has a positive and significant direct effect on organizational loyalty, belongingness has a positive and significant direct effect on organizational loyalty, leadership Ethical has a positive and significant direct effect on the variable of work attachment and ethical leadership with an indirect path coefficient through work attachment has an indirect, positive and significant effect on organizational loyalty at the 50% level. Also, ethical leadership has been able to explain 47% of the variance of organizational loyalty due to emotional attachment (26). Tayibi Abolhasani and Khodabakhshi conducted research entitled "Factors affecting the durability of knowledge human resources in knowledge-based companies". They conducted their study in a qualitative-exploratory way with content analysis method based on semi-structured interviews with 9 successful knowledge-based companies located in growth centers and science and technology parks. In his research, coding and categorization methods were used to analyze the data, and finally, effective factors were identified and analyzed in the form of 17 components and 3 individual, organizational, and environmental categories (27).

Esmaili and Saidzadeh conducted research entitled "Effect of job satisfaction on performance with the mediating role of organizational loyalty (case study: Jihad Agriculture Organization of Ilam province)" and concluded that job satisfaction directly with a path coefficient of 53 percent and indirectly with the mediating role of organizational loyalty has a direct effect on job performance with a path coefficient of 62 percent. Also, job satisfaction has a positive effect on organizational loyalty with a path coefficient of 74% and organizational loyalty has a positive effect on job performance with a path coefficient of 76% (28). Ranjbar and Shafizadeh conducted a research entitled "Identification and prioritization of factors affecting the survival and permanence of employees of the 13th district of Tehran" and concluded that job and organizational factors such as job security, job promotion, organizational justice, insurance, and social security Also, financial and economic topics such as salaries and benefits, financial rewards and loan facilities are among the important factors in this field, and according to the employees, they are more prioritized than other factors (29). Qalipour, Amiri, Mahdizadeh, and Zamani Far conducted research entitled "Identification of the factors affecting the retention of knowledge workers in the Iran Oil Products Refining and Distribution Company" and concluded that there is a difference between the opinion of knowledge workers and their managers about the influence of the factors Considered there is a difference. In a situation where the employees put the variables of public education, independence, social support, and payment as their priority, managers emphasized job satisfaction, payment, social support, and justice (30).

Bakotik conducted research titled "Relationship between job satisfaction and performance" and concluded that job satisfaction plays a greater role in determining performance than the role of performance in determining job satisfaction (31). Fadlallah conducted research titled "Effect of job satisfaction on employee performance (research on Faculty of Science and Humanities Studies of Salman Ibn Abdulaziz University)" and concluded that there is a positive and significant relationship between job satisfaction factors and employee performance (32). Javad Baloch and Hassan conducted research titled "Determinants of job satisfaction and its effect on employee performance and intentions to quit" and concluded that the factors of employee empowerment, work environment, loyalty, and job performance have a positive and significant correlation with job satisfaction. have (33). Janja and Golzar, in their research entitled "Effect of human resource measures on employee commitment and employee retention in the telecommunications sector of Pakistan by examining the mediating role of employee loyalty" concluded that various human resource measures have a significant effect on employee commitment and retention. Also, loyalty mediates the relationship between human resource management and employee commitment and retention (34). Kang and Thien conducted research entitled "Effective factors on employee loyalty directly and indirectly through job satisfaction (case study: State-owned banking of Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam)" and concluded that higher levels of satisfaction are positively correlated with higher levels of organizational loyalty. has it. By using path analysis, it was found that greater loyalty requires achieving greater job satisfaction (35).

Alnakyoubi, in research titled "Relationships between human resource measures and employee retention in government organizations" sought to identify the impact of human resource measures and other factors, such as job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and leadership on employee retention. The results showed the importance of the effect and significance of these factors on employee retention (36). Patriota conducted a study entitled "Employee Retention: An Integrated View of Human Resource Support Measures and Perceived Organizational Support in Swedish Organizations" and concluded that measures such as growth opportunities, job challenges, pay, and relations between managers and employees, have had a significant effect on the retention of key employees of the studied organizations. Also, employees' perception of HR support measures has been effective in the development of perceived organizational support and their job satisfaction (37).

Research Questions

According to the purpose of the research "identification and ranking" in which the hypothesis was not mentioned; As a result, the research questions were designed and compiled as follows:

The main question: What is the appropriate model of organizational loyalty and retention of faculty members of the University of Medical Sciences?

Sub questions:

1. What are the effective factors on organizational loyalty and retention of faculty members of the University of Medical Sciences?
2. What is the ranking of the factors affecting the organizational loyalty and retention of faculty members of the University of Medical Sciences?
3. What is the status of the University of Medical Sciences in terms of organizational loyalty and tenure of faculty members?

Research Method

The current study is applied in terms of purpose and descriptive survey in terms of type, which is the effective factors of organizational loyalty and retention of faculty members of Mashhad University of Medical Sciences using the hierarchical method and comparing two-by-two socio-statistical opinions (pairwise comparison of indicators). Therefore, to compare pairs of indicators and determine the importance coefficient (weight) of factors affecting the loyalty and retention of faculty members of Mashhad University of Medical Sciences, a hierarchical analysis questionnaire (nine-point scale and two-by-two comparison) was used, based on the hierarchy tree. The levels of the studied problem were proposed. The hierarchy analysis process is one of the multi-indicator decision-making methods that is used to decide and choose one option from among many decision options, and for this purpose, the indicators determined by the decision-maker are used. This method starts with the decision hierarchy tree and reflects natural behavior and human thinking based on pairwise comparisons. The decision hierarchy tree shows the factors to be compared and the competing options to be evaluated in the decision. Then a series of pairwise comparisons is performed, and the result of these pairwise comparisons determines the weight of each factor in line with the competing options. Finally, the matrices obtained from pairwise comparisons are combined in such a way that the optimal decision is obtained (38).

The statistical population of the research was the faculty members of Mashhad University of Medical Sciences with at least a doctorate and ten years of experience, who were working under the management of the university's faculty affairs in the affiliated faculties of the university. The sample size was determined based on Morgan's table and the samples were selected according to the proportionality of the population size in each group and in each group in a stratified simple random manner. However, since some of the collected questionnaires were incomplete and distorted, finally 169 questionnaires were analyzed and reviewed. In the current research, after reviewing the theoretical foundations studying more than 20 articles, and examining the effective factors of organizational loyalty and retention of faculty members of Mashhad University of Medical Sciences, a set of related factors and indicators were extracted and identified and using the opinion of experts and Experts in the field of management and human resources (group of experts) were selected and categorized. The confirmed factors were merged due to similarity and overlap and finally, in the form of 3 factors and 3 antecedents prone to influence in the form of 41 propositions, they were placed as main and secondary factors for pairwise comparisons. In the following, the extracted propositions were presented in the form of a questionnaire and were approved by 20 experts (including university professors and selected members of the investigated statistical community).

To measure the reliability of the effective factors and propositions of this stage, Cronbach's alpha coefficient was calculated, which indicated that there was no significant difference in the comments. After that, the subjects were asked to make a pairwise comparison of the influencing factors. Expert Choice 2000 software package (an version of group hierarchical analysis) was used to perform the hierarchical analysis method. This software is necessarily designed for group decision-making patterns and has extensive facilities for obtaining pairs of people's matrices and then combining the matrix of different people and turning it into a single matrix, which is obtained through the geometric mean of individual elements of the people's matrices. The basis of this software is that first, it receives the information of the questionnaires and after combining it, based on each of the criteria, it performs the corresponding ranking along with the compatibility rate of each one, and finally, by combining all the criteria, reports the ranking and overall compliance rate (39).

Demographic information of subjects

The results presented in Table 1 show that 80.85% of the subjects were men and 14.20% were women; 40.83% of the subjects had a doctorate, 33.73% had a specialized doctorate and 24.85% had a professional doctorate; 46.75% of the subjects were members of educational faculty and 52.07% were members of research faculty; 26.63% have the scientific rank of instructor, 27.81% have the scientific rank of assistant professor, 19.53% have the scientific rank of associate professor, 23.67% have the scientific rank of professor; 20.71% had 10 to 15 years of experience, 23.68% had 16 to 20 years of experience, 21.89% had 21 to 25 years of experience, 32.54% had more than 25 years of experience, and also the subjects In the Faculty of Medicine with 74.56%, the highest number of participants and the Faculty of Traditional Medicine with 1.18%, the lowest number of participants. These results show that the subjects have the necessary conditions to answer the questionnaire of the current research.

Table 1: Demographic information

Index	Variable	Frequency	Frequency Percentage
Gender	Male	145	85/8
	Female	24	14/2
Degree	P.H.D	69	83/40
	Ph.D	57	73/33
	Professional doctorate	42	85/24
The scientific group	Educational faculty member	79	46/73
	Research faculty member	88	52/07
The scientific rank of the instructor	The coach	45	63/26
	Assistant Professor	47	81/27
	Associate Professor	33	53/19
	Professor	40	67/23
Length of work experience	10 to 15 years	35	71/20
	16 to 20 years	40	68/23
	21 to 25 years	37	89/21
	More than 25 years	55	54/32
University	Faculty of medicine	126	56/74
	Faculty of Health	6	55/3
	Faculty of Nursing	9	33/5
	Faculty of Pharmacy	8	73/4
	Faculty of Dentistry	18	65/10
	Faculty of traditional medicine	2	1/18

Findings

In this research, to calculate the relative importance (weight) of each of the indicators based on the hierarchical method, a two-by-two comparison of the opinions of the statistical community has been used. The survey indicators included

environmental factors (a), organizational factors (b), individual factors (c), job satisfaction (d), organizational commitment (e) and organizational belonging (f). The normalized matrix of these indicators is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Normalized matrix (main criterion)

Index	A	B	C	D	E	F
A	0.32	0.40	0.352	0.224	0.242	0.291
B	0.19	0.12	0.253	0.41	0.227	0.249
C	0.11	0.24	0.125	0.111	0.194	0.136
D	0.19	0.08	0.153	0.136	0.22	0.139
E	0.08	0.07	0.043	0.041	0.066	0.105
F	0.08	0.07	0.074	0.079	0.051	0.08

Following the calculated weights of second-level elements (factors) in each subgroup (index), the basis for evaluating the priority and degree of importance of each factor was placed. As a result, the final weight of the elements of each group (the factor of each index) was obtained by multiplying the local weight of the elements by the weight of their group head (the index) and the factors affecting the organizational loyalty and retention of faculty members of Mashhad University of Medical Sciences were ranked. Table 3 shows the ranking of the factors affecting the organizational loyalty and retention of faculty members of Mashhad University of Medical Sciences: the first rank is related to the factor of access to scientific resources, information, and modern technology (A1) with a relative weight of 0.4302. The second rank is related to the factor of decent and respectful behavior of the manager with the employees (B4) with a relative weight of 0.3463. The third rank is related to the factor of bureaucracy and paperwork in the organization (B1) with a relative weight of 0.3208.

The fourth rank is related to the factor of having an evaluation and control system to receive quick and regular feedback from the work (B3) with a relative weight of 0.3014. The fifth rank is related to the factor of stress or low job security (B7) with a relative weight of 0.2990. The sixth rank is related to the factor of awareness of career promotion path (B6) with a relative weight of 0.2860. The seventh rank is related to the factor of satisfaction with the establishment of justice and non-discrimination (T7) with a relative weight of 0.1984. The eighth rank is related to the factor of handling and paying attention to criticisms and suggestions (T3) with a relative weight of 0.1681. The ninth rank is related to the factor of government support for organizations with high-level technology (A4) with a relative weight of 0.1536. The tenth rank is related to the factor of forming interdisciplinary teams (collaborating with the best in the field) (P7) with a relative weight of 0.1374. The eleventh rank is related to the possibility of using modern technology (P3) with a relative weight of 0.1338.

The twelfth rank is related to the factor of minimum positional difference between employees (D7) with a relative weight of 0.1166. The thirteenth rank is related to the factor of creating problem-solving groups (D6) with a relative weight of 0.1091. The 14th rank is related to the motivation factor with fostering opportunities for growth, learning, and career development (C1) with a relative weight of 0.0980. The fifteenth rank is related to the factor of justice in payments (B5) with a relative weight of 0.0979. The 16th rank is related to the compatibility factor of workgroup goals and organizational goals (9) with a relative weight of 0.0973. The 17th rank is related to the job flexibility factor (D8) with a relative weight of 0.0821. The 18th rank is related to the job expectations factor (D1) with a relative weight of 0.0820. The 19th rank is related to the factor of cultural attitude about style and responsibility in life (A2) with a relative weight of 0.0814. The 20th rank is related to the job selection factor (T2) with a relative weight of 0.0793. The 21st rank is related to the

factor of satisfaction with the appointment following services and individual competence (T6) with a relative weight of 0.0766. The 22nd rank is related to the factor of providing equipment and knowledge required for high-tech industries (A3) with a relative weight of 0.0652.

The twenty-third rank is related to the communication system efficiency factor (B2) with a relative weight of 0.0575. The twenty-fourth rank is related to the factor of satisfaction with commuting service (T4) with a relative weight of 0.0526. The 25th rank is related to the psychological contract factor (T3) with a relative weight of 0.0498. The twenty-sixth rank is related to the personality compatibility factor with the job (P6) with a relative weight of 0.0468. The twenty-seventh rank is related to the factor relating to job requirements and belonging (vitality and dedication) (C4) with a relative weight of 0.0377. The twenty-eighth rank is related to the factor of the opportunity to gain global experience and knowledge (P2) with a relative weight of 0.0354. The twenty-ninth rank is related to the factor of justice in work planning (T2) with a relative weight of 0.0344. The 30th rank is related to the factor of access to tools and equipment (P4) with a relative weight of 0.0327. The 31st rank is related to the factor of satisfaction with the timely promotion of rank and group (T5) with a relative weight of 0.0302. The thirty-second rank is related to the learning and growth opportunity factor (P1) with a relative weight of 0.0270. The 33rd rank is related to the organization characteristics factor (S4) with a relative weight of 0.0239.

The thirty-fourth rank is related to the factor of becoming one with work (P5) with a relative weight of 0.0217. The 35th rank is related to the factor of satisfaction and familiarity with the description of assigned tasks (T1) with a relative weight of 0.0157. The thirty-sixth rank is related to the factor of the existence of organizational platforms that support the needs and demands of employees (C5) with a relative weight of 0.0156. The thirty-seventh rank is related to the manager's commitment to long-term career development and training in the workplace (D10) with a relative weight of 0.0139. The 38th rank is related to the feeling of ability factor in a successful effect on the environment (C3) with a relative weight of 0.0101. The thirty-ninth rank is related to the motivation factor due to its instrumental role in achieving goals (C2) with a relative weight of 0.0065. The 40th rank is related to the information dissemination factor (T5) with a relative weight of 0.0046. The 41st rank is related to the factor of lack of access to alternative jobs (D11) with a relative weight of 0.0037.

Table 3: Ranking of effective factors of organizational loyalty and retention of faculty members of Mashhad University of Medical Sciences by AHP hierarchy method.

Main factors (indices)	Weight of main factors (indices)	Sub-factors	Local weight Sub-factors	Final weight	Rank/Priority
A	0.306	A1	1.406	0.4302	1
		A2	0.266	0.0814	19
		A3	0.213	0.0652	22
		A4	0.502	0.3208	9
B	0.266	B1	1.206	0.3208	3
		B2	0.216	0.0575	23
		B3	1.133	0.3014	4
		B4	1.302	0.3463	2
		B5	0.368	0.0979	15

		B6	1.075	0.2860	6
		B7	1.124	0.2990	5
P	0.133	P1	0.203	0.0270	32
		P2	0.266	0.0354	28
		P3	1.006	0.1338	11
		P4	0.246	0.0327	30
		P5	0.163	0.0217	34
		P6	0.352	0.0468	26
		P7	0.133	0.1374	10
T	0.152	T1	0.103	0.0157	35
		T2	0.226	0.0344	29
		T3	0.106	0.1681	8
		T4	0.346	0.0526	24
		T5	0.199	0.0302	31
		T6	0.504	0.0766	21
		T7	1.305	0.1984	7
D	0.068	D1	1.206	0.0820	18
		D2	1.166	0.0793	20
		D3	0.733	0.0498	25
		D4	0.352	0.0239	33
		D5	0.068	0.0046	40
		D6	1.605	0.1091	13
		D7	0.714	0.1166	12
		D8	1.208	0.0821	17
		D9	1.431	0.0973	16
		D10	0.204	0.0139	37
		D11	0.054	0.0037	41
C	0.075	C1	1.306	0.0980	14
		C2	0.086	0.0065	39
		C3	0.134	0.0101	38
		C4	0.502	0.0377	27
		C5	0.208	0.0156	36

Conclusion

Today, organizations are successful and have high flexibility. This requires employee participation and efficient interaction at all levels. Human resources are the most valuable competitive advantage in organizations and as much as they can cause the success and survival of the organization; They may be a serious obstacle in the way of the organization; In some cases, employees may tend to behave in ways that do not comply with the organizational norms and thereby threaten their health and that of other employees. The occurrence of such work behaviors can hurt the organization and employees; Organizations seek to identify and specify destructive behaviors to achieve professionalism and seek to create appropriate frameworks to act in that direction.

The low motivation of the faculty members due to the low quality of the outputs affects the name of the university scientifically, which causes a smaller number of elites to attend the university as students, and reduces the prestige of the university, and this cycle will repeat itself. On the other hand, the low quality of incoming students gradually affects the faculty members negatively. In colleges, the number of students is small, and their age is high; For this reason, the quality of the students is low, which causes the professor to lower the level of the material, and gradually (with a delay), the quality of the professor also weakens. A weak teacher leads to a weak student and this cycle weakens itself in the same way.

Also, the entry of quality students will make the graduates of the faculties enjoy higher quality and thus bring more credit, this credit will cause the entry of more quality students, and even the central organization will be ready to send its quality forces to study in the colleges. Therefore, the quality of the graduates will increase again, and then the credibility of the faculties will increase, and by repeating the cycle, it will be strengthened. However, the lower the level of the existing academic staff, the lower the quality of the work output of the academic staff, and as a result, the credibility of the faculty will decrease, and skepticism and mistrust of the faculty will increase. And gradually, the quality level of the members will decrease, and the output will decrease again, and this vicious cycle will continue.

With the production of higher quality outputs of the faculty members and as a result more credibility of the faculties, the central organization also feels more need for them and makes more efforts for more support and structural, financial support, investment for research and attention to academic centers and in the future, He will refer to the faculty to solve his problems. This support and reference will lead to the presence of more members in the central organization and their knowledge of it, and will increase the quality and, as a result, increase their outputs, and this cycle will be repeated. On the other hand, the credibility of the faculties affects the amount of investment of the central organization and the individual's reference to the faculty and faculty, and it will make the sense of identity felt in the faculty and faculty and increase the motivation, quality of the faculty and the quality of their outputs. In this way, the reputation of the university will be increased, the investment and referral will be more, and the cycle will be repeated. But as it was said before, to solve some of its problems, the central organization turns to parallel activities such as creating research centers and using professors from other faculties, which will enable it to reduce its investment and referral to faculties. Of course, the blind spot of this policy is that the strategic and fundamental issues of the organization have not been resolved in the long term, which causes parallel activities and reduces the quality of the output of the faculty and the prestige of the faculty.

The low quality of faculty outputs leads the university authorities to think of applying stricter control mechanisms to them, but these systems reduce the sense of dignity in them (the sense of lowering the dignity of professors and uniting It creates with employees) and reduce motivation, and thus affect their quality. For this reason, the quality of the professors' output has decreased, and the authorities are again applying stricter mechanisms than in the past. Because they think that the existing mechanisms are not strict enough to motivate the members to work and make more effort. The blind spot of this policy is that this type of control reduces the internal motivation of the members and according to the metaphor of the tortoise, it makes them defensive so that they can somehow comply with the appearance and pass the system safely and get promoted. This cycle always reinforces itself and every time stricter rules are applied and demotivates the members. As the culture of science increases in the central organization is strengthened, the scientific dominance of the university in the central organization will increase, and this will lead to more respect for the university

and the faculty and, as a result, a greater sense of dignity for the professors, thus increasing motivation and increasing the quality of the output. will follow theirs.

Qualitative outputs have increased the credibility of the faculties and resulted in more support and referrals to faculty members, these support and referrals have strengthened the culture of seeking knowledge in the central organization and this cycle will be repeated regularly. The more the culture of seeking knowledge in the central organization is strengthened, the more support and referrals it will have to the university and the faculty, and as a result, it will make more efforts to create a platform and provide role-creating fields for the professors in the central organization, and thus the faculty officially through the central organization will be accepted. This is considered as a kind of identity induction to the university and will create a sense of identity in the members. The sense of identity motivates and increases the quality of outputs and increases the prestige of the university, and subsequently, it will strengthen the culture of seeking knowledge in the organization and intensify the mentioned cycle again.

The motivation of faculty members is a very effective factor in strengthening their organizational loyalty and longevity. Other factors such as a sense of dignity, sense of identity, members' trust in the system, stability and peace in the university, leadership style of the central organization and the university, control mechanisms, sense of security, stability of university policies and other factors are effective in the motivation of professors, and they encourage them to try and, in this way, affects their quality.

Different personality traits and beliefs determine their goals, objectives, and expectations from the university; To the extent that university activities and services match people's expectations, motivation increases and otherwise, it has the opposite effect. Of course, sometimes faculty members, despite being aware of the unfavorable social, political, and economic conditions in the university, do not stop trying in various fields to improve the conditions due to their internal motivation. But at the organizational level, sometimes there may be a series of pressures on faculty members due to a certain political atmosphere governing the university, which causes them to be dissatisfied; However, some factors are from the old traditions of the university and have been institutionalized in it; For example, less trust in young people, discussion of seniority and history in the distribution of courses and distribution of theses, as well as relationism between people can be the source of many misfortunes.

Future researchers are suggested to investigate the factors affecting organizational loyalty and tenure of faculty members of other universities. Also, identity-building factors for the faculties and faculty members of the university and factors affecting the increase in the culture of science in the university should be identified and studied. However, the factors affecting organizational loyalty and longevity of university faculty members can be influenced by organizational structures, managers' behavioral style, and taste, market conditions, and changes in the internal and external (and even political) environment. The results of the research are related to Mashhad University of Medical Sciences.

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